

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Reducing damage from ploughing

Mouldboard ploughing can result in serious damage to soil structure and biology. The damage is caused by a combination of soil inversion which buries plant residue, leaving the soil bare for extended periods, and compaction damage from the furrow wheel. These can be reduced considerably with proper timing and technique.

Firstly, the shallower the ploughing depth, the less the damage to soil organisms. Secondly, adding a loosening blade under the plough share can allow shallower inversion with sufficient depth loosening. The lowest acceptable depth depends on many conditions. But it is useful to ask, how deep does the soil need to be tilled in the first place?

Minimizing the time that the soil remains bare after tillage reduces both damage to biology and erosion risks. Either ploughing right before planting the crop, or planting a cover crop after ploughing are good practices. Leveling and consolidating

the soil after ploughing can reduce excessive drying and restore pore connectivity. These can in some situations be done during ploughing with furrow crackers and presses.

Blunt plough shares compress and shape the soil to a plough-pan, especially in moist conditions. Timing the ploughing to the right soil conditions and maintaining the cutting edge reduce compaction from the plough itself, but leave possible the compaction from the tractor.

The main compaction risk is the furrow wheel, which runs directly on the subsoil. Moving the tractor on-land with a specialty plow is an option, but they can be expensive. Especially for non-reversible ploughs, the headstock can be modified to allow on-land ploughing with less cost. Another option is to use extra wide tyres or even dual wheels, which work on some soil types but require re-adjusting the plough.

1. During ploughing the furrow wheel compacts the subsoil, root channels are disturbed and the soil loses cover.

KEYWORDS

Tillage, soil degradation, soil management, settings, on-land ploughing

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817819

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